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MYCOTOXINS IN HERBS AND SPICES – OVERVIEW OF RASFF NOTIFICATIONS

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The primary task of the European Union Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) is to ensure rapid and efficient exchange of information about health risks associated with food, with the aim of reducing potential negative impacts on public health. Herbs and spices are a category of food commonly contaminated with mycotoxins, specifically aflatoxins, characterised as potent hepatocarcinogens, and nephrotoxin ochratoxin A. Bearing in mind the wide use of herbs and spices in culinary practices, the aim of the present study was to monitor such contamination, based on data from the RASFF database for the period 2010 – 2023. A total of 566 notifications were recorded for the food category „herbs and spices“ and hazard category „mycotoxins“. There were significantly more notifications concerning the presence of aflatoxins – 453 (80.0%), while the presence of ochratoxin A was noted in 124 samples. The majority of notifications resulted from border controls, with 413 cases (73.0%), followed by official control on the market (22.4%) and the company’s own check (4.6%). In 227 cases (40.0%), the raw material originated from India, followed by a smaller number of notifications from Indonesia, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Ethiopia, China, etc. The predominant spices contaminated with mycotoxins were chili, chili peppers and paprika (taken together, responsible for 47.2% of all notifications) and nutmeg (24.6%). Concentrations of aflatoxins were highly variable, in several cases exceeding 0.2 mg/kg (nutmeg) or even 0.3 mg/kg (peppers) of total aflatoxins (maximum allowed 0.010 mg/kg), The highest ochratoxin A concentration was recorded in organic dandelion root (0.570 mg/kg; 0.020 mg/kg allowed). The risk decision for as many as 468 notifications (82.7%) was considered as serious, resulting in 372 cases of border rejection. Considering the widespread view that RASFF reveals only the tip of the iceberg, the presented findings should be regarded as clear warning for public health professionals.

Keywords: aflatoxins, ochratoxin A, food safety, public health